

Formal oxidative addition of dioxygen to coordinated carbon monoxide. Isolation and characterization of ruthenium carbonate complex of 2-(aryloxy)pyridine[†]

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Abstract : The reaction of Ru₃(CO)₁₂ with 2,6-dichlorophenylazopyridine (L) in boiling n-octane under positive pressure of di-oxygen affords a blue complex of composition [Ru^{II}(CO₃)L₂]. This reaction exemplifies an unusual chemical transformation wherein the anionic bidentate carbonate, CO₃²⁻ is formed *in situ* by formal addition of O₂ via activation of coordinated carbon monoxide. The Ru-carbonate complex is characterized by X-ray crystallographic structure analysis nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry, ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy, electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy, and density functional theory. The complex displays one reversible electron transfer process at -0.28 V along with two irreversible electron transfer process near -1.23 and 1.42 V. The response at negative potential is due to reduction of the coordinated azo-function. The reversible reductive process is characterized by EPR spectroscopy. Density functional theory calculations have been employed to confirm structural features and to support their spectral and redox properties.

Keywords : Coordination chemistry, formal oxidative di-oxygen activation, X-ray structure, redox properties, ruthenium carbonate.

Introduction

Among various azoaromatic compounds we have long-standing interest in the coordination chemistry of 2-(aryloxy)pyridine (2-aop) ligands due to its versatile coordination and redox chemistry. In recent years we and others have demonstrated that azo-aromatics can act as dominant electron sink in their metal complexes¹⁻⁶. Due to the presence of low-lying π* molecular orbitals it can accept electron(s) chemically or electrochemically to produce complexes of azo-mono-anion radical or hydrazido di-anion ligands⁷⁻⁹. Further addition of two electrons to a hydrazido dianion leads to the rupture of the [N-N]²⁻ bond (Scheme 1). In recent years, reductive cleavage of azo function followed by intermolecular chemical transformations were noted in few instances wherein nucleophilic attack of phenylimido or pyridylimido occur at

the coordinated azo-aromatic ligands¹⁰⁻¹³. Very recently we came across to another unusual chemical reaction involving azo cleavage vis-à-vis nucleophilic attack of the pyridylimido moiety at coordinated carbon monoxide in a zero-valent carbonyl complex of ruthenium¹³.

In this report we describe yet another unprecedented chemical reaction of formal addition of oxygen to coordinated CO which has led to isolation of a ruthenium carbonate complex. When Ru₃(CO)₁₂ and 2,6-dichlorophenylazopyridine (L) are allowed to react in presence of positive pressure of di-oxygen substitution of (CO) by ligand L along with CO activation vis-à-vis formal oxygen addition occurs. The isolated complex is characterized by a variety of physical techniques. The primary chemical transformation is as in Scheme 2.

Scheme 1. Electron transfer series of azo function.

Scheme 2

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

In this context it is worth noting that there have been reports of nucleophilic attack of oxygen containing nucleophiles like OH^- , OCH_3^- to coordinated CO in metal carbonyls which in fact is the key step in homogeneous catalysis of water gas shift reaction in alkaline conditions¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The synthetic protocol for the synthesis of the above carbonate complex is otherwise different from the conventional procedure where dichlorides salts are treated with Ag_2CO_3 ¹⁷.

Experimental

Materials :

The starting material, $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ is an Aldrich reagent. The ligand was prepared by following a reported procedure¹⁸. Tetrabutylammoniumperchlorate was prepared and recrystallised following the published procedure¹⁹. *Caution! Perchlorates must be handled with care and appropriate safety precautions!* All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and used as received.

Instrumentation :

UV-Vis absorption spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Infrared spectrum was obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out in 0.1 M $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]\text{ClO}_4$ solutions using a three-electrode configuration (platinum working electrode, Pt counter electrode, Ag/AgCl reference) and a PC-controlled PAR model 273A electrochemistry system. A Pt wire gauge working electrode was used for exhaustive electrolyses. The $E_{1/2}$ for the ferrocenium-ferrocene couple under our experimental condition was 0.40 V. The peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) for the Fc/Fc^+ (Fc^+ = ferrocenium ion) couple under the experimental conditions was 80 mV. A Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (C, H, N). ESI mass spectrum was recorded on a micro mass Q-TOF mass spectrometer (Serial no. YA 263). EPR spectrum in the X band was recorded with a JEOL JES-FA200 spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectrum was taken on a Bruker Advance DPX 400 spectrometer and SiMe_4 was used as the internal standard.

Synthesis of complex $\text{Ru}(\text{L})_2(\text{CO})_3$, **1** :

A mixture of 100 mg of $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ (0.15 mmol) and 227 mg of L (0.90 mmol) was refluxed in n-octane in presence of positive pressure of di-oxygen for 3 h when the color of the solution became bluish violet. The crude mass obtained by evaporation of the solution, was purified on a preparative alumina TLC plate using the solvent

mixture chloroform/acetonitrile (5 : 2) as eluent, a distinct blue band separated, which was extracted by methanol and collected by evaporation of the solvent. Finally, it was recrystallized by slow diffusion of a dichloromethane solution of the compound into hexane. Yield : 35% (109 mg). Anal. (%) : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Ru}$: C, 41.52; H, 2.12; N, 12.63. Found : C, 42.21; H, 2.08; N, 12.42; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1631 [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$], 1244 [$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$], 1293 [$\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$]; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.61 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.36 (1H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 8.02 (1H, t, J 7.4 Hz), 7.46 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz), 7.398 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz), 7.17 (1H, t, J 8 Hz), 6.88 (1H, d, J 8 Hz); ESI-MS m/z 688.83 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

X-Ray crystallography :

Crystallographic data for the complex **1** was collected in Table 1. Suitable X-ray quality crystals were obtained by slow diffusion of a dichloromethane solution of the complex into hexane. Data were collected on a Bruker

Table 1. Crystallographic data of **1**

1	
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Ru}$
Molecular mass	665.27
Temperature (K)	293
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
a (Å)	11.654(5)
b (Å)	17.946(5)
c (Å)	12.003(5)
α (deg)	90
β (deg)	93.971(5)
γ (deg)	90
V (Å ³)	2504.3(17)
Z	4
D_{calcd} (g/cm ³)	1.765
Cryst. dims. (mm)	0.09 × 0.12 × 0.14
θ range for data coll. (deg)	2.3–32.2
GOF	0.94
Reflns. collected	19094
Uniq. reflns.	4016
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	R = 0.0222
	wR2 = 0.0768

SMART APEX-II diffractometer, equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) and were corrected for Lorentz polarization effects. **1** : A

total of 19094 reflections were collected, of which 4016 were unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.019$), satisfying the $I > 2\sigma(I)$ criterion, and were used in subsequent analysis. The structures were solved by employing the SHELXS-97 program package²⁰ and were refined by full-matrix least squares based on F^2 (SHELXL-97)²¹. All hydrogen atoms were added in calculated positions.

Computational methods, DFT calculations :

All DFT calculations presented in this paper were carried out using the Gaussian 09 program package²². Geometry optimizations were performed without imposing geometric constraints (C_1 symmetry), and stationary points were subsequently confirmed to be minima by vibrational analysis (no imaginary frequencies). The hybrid B3LYP²³ exchange-correlation functional was used in conjunction with the SDD basis set with effective core potential for the Ru atom²⁴. For all other atoms C, H, N, polarized 6-31G(d,p) basis sets was used. The calculations of the complexes were performed using either spin-restricted or spin-unrestricted approaches. Mulliken spin densities were used for analysis of the spin populations on ligand and metal centers. Singlet excitation energies based on the solvent-phase (CH_2Cl_2) optimized geometry of the compound **1** and its reduced complex were computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism²⁵ in dichloromethane using the conductor-like polarizable continuum model²⁶. GAUSSSUM²⁷ was used to calculate the percentage contribution of ligand and metal to the frontier orbital and the fractional contributions of various molecular orbitals in the optical spectral transition.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Reaction of $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ (0.1 mmol) with L (0.6 mmol) in boiling n-octane in presence of positive pressure of dioxygen produced a new carbonate complex of ruthenium(II), $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{L}_2(\text{CO}_3)$, **1** in a moderate yield.

We have chosen Ru^0 carbonyl as the starting material with the anticipation that substitution followed by internal electron(s) transfer would lead to successful isolation of various types of redox induced chemically transformed complexes. Moreover an example of $4e^-$ reductive cleavage of arylazo substrate via internal electron transfer from

Ru^0 was noted by us recently where *in situ* generated arylimide di-anion attacks the ruthenium coordinated carbon monoxide to result a carbamoyl complex of Ru^{II} ¹³. However a completely different course of reaction set in when the above reaction was carried out in positive pressure of O_2 . Electron transfer to O_2 followed by nucleophilic attack of O_2^{2-} (peroxide) to a coordinated CO produced the bis-chelated carbonate complex as shown in Scheme 3. The reaction resulted in a bi-valent ruthenium complex, which involves two following redox process : (i) $\text{Ru}^0 \rightarrow \text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ (ii) $\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{O}_2^{2-}$. A minor quantity of the previously reported carbamoyl complex was also identified in the reaction mixture. So as an outcome of this result it may be concluded that $2e^-$ reduction of O_2 is preferred over $4e^-$ reductive azo cleavage reaction (Scheme 4).

Microanalytical, positive-ion ESI-MS, together with NMR spectrum of the above carbonate complex convincingly support its formulation. For example, the complex showed an intense peak at m/z 688.8 amu in acetonitrile due to $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ and its simulated spectrum matched well with the experimental one. The ESI-MS spectrum of the complex along with simulated one is shown in Fig. 1. The complex possesses a $S = 0$ ground state as determined by its room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement and displayed sharp ^1H NMR resonances in the normal range for diamagnetic compound. The low number of resonances for the complex indicates high symmetry of the molecule in solutions. All seven aromatic protons resonances for one ligand are distinct and visible in the range 8.6–6.8 ppm. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the complex in CDCl_3 is shown in Fig. 2. The complex showed strong absorption in FTIR at 1631 and 1244 cm^{-1} which is characteristic for ionic carbonate function^{28–30}. Notably the vibration frequency $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ in **1** is lower (1292 cm^{-1}) compared to that of the uncoordinated ligand $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ (1437 cm^{-1}), which is attributed to $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-L}(\pi^*)$ interactions.

Moreover effervesce was noted when the complex was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The corresponding dichloride complex **3** (Scheme 5) was isolated and characterized spectroscopically. Data of this complex **3** is submitted as Supplementary information (Fig. S1).

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Fig. 1. ESI-MS spectra of complex 1. [(lower) experimental; (upper) simulated].

X-Ray crystallography :

The complex 1 formed suitable crystals for X-ray diffraction studies. ORTEP and partial atom numbering schemes of the above complex is shown in Fig. 3 and selected bond parameters are collected in Table 2 and

crystallographic details are collected in Table 1. Structural analysis of 1 confirmed the identity of the reference molecule. The isolated molecule, 1 has a crystallographic C_2 symmetry that makes half of the molecule identical with the other half. Overall the molecule is hexa-coordinated and coordination sphere has a distorted octahedral geometry. In this mixed ligand complex, Ru atom is bonded to two L and a carbonate CO_3^{2-} anion. The ligand L is coordinated as a usual neutral N,N-donor with $d_{\text{N-N}}$ of 1.292(2) Å. Elongation of $d_{\text{N-N}}$ distance in this complex indicates strong $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-L}(\pi^*)$ interactions. For comparison the $d_{\text{N-N}}$ distance in free L is ~ 1.24 Å. Ru-O distance is 2.0605(14) Å which is typically a single bond. The two C-O bond lengths in the complexes are different : $d_{\text{C}(12)\text{-O}(2)}$ is 1.226(3) Å and $d_{\text{C}(12)\text{-O}(1)}$ is 1.3224(18) Å respectively. Similar behavior is noted in related metal carbonate complexes.

Scheme 5

Cyclic voltammetry and EPR :

Redox properties of complex 1 were examined by cyclic voltammetry in dichloromethane solution containing 0.1 M $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]\text{ClO}_4$ as the supporting electrolyte in the potential range from +1.6 V to -1.6 V, using platinum disk as the working electrode. The potentials are referenced to the saturated Ag/AgCl electrode and the results are summarized in Table 3. The $E_{1/2}$ value of the ferrocenium-ferrocene couple, under our experimental conditions, was 0.40 V. The stoichiometry of the redox processes was confirmed by the coulomb count of constant-potential electrolysis experiments for the reversible waves. Cyclic voltammetry of complex 1 exhibited one reversible electron transfer (ET) process at potentials –

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of complex **1** in CDCl_3 . [Inset : Aromatic proton resonances].

0.28 V together with two irreversible ET processes at a potential of -1.23 and $+1.42$ V (Fig. 4, full voltammogram Fig. S2). To gain further insight into the electron transfer

Fig. 3. ORTEP of complex **1**. Hydrogen atoms are removed for clarity.

Table 2. Selected experimental and calculated bond distances of complex **1**

	1		[1] ⁻
	Expt.	Calcd.	Calcd.
Ru-N1	2.0145(17)	2.052	2.069
Ru-N3	1.9853(16)	2.056	2.032
N2-N3	1.297(2)	1.292	1.337
Ru-O1	2.0605(14)	2.057	2.082
C12-O1	1.3224(18)	1.344	1.338
C12-O2	1.226(3)	1.213	1.223

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric and spectral data of the complex **1**

Complex	Cyclic voltammetric data ^a	UV-Vis spectral data ^d
	$E_{1/2}$ ^b (V), ΔE_p (mV)	λ_{max} ^d (nm), ϵ ($10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)
1	-1.23^c , -0.28 (90), 1.42^c	860 (0.05), 620 (1.1), 460 (0.16) ^e , 370 (0.5) ^e , 300 (1.169)

^aDichloromethane solution (supporting electrolyte Bu_4NClO_4); working electrode platinum, reference electrode Ag/AgCl . ^b $E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})$ where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials respectively, $\Delta E_p = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}$, scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} . ^cIrreversible. ^dWavelength in nm, molar extinction coefficients in $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in dichloromethane solvent. ^eShoulder.

Fig. 4. Segmented cyclic voltammogram of the complex **1** in dichloromethane (0.1 M TBAP). [Inset : EPR spectrum of electrogenerated reduced complex [**1**]^{•-}].

events associated with the reversible ET processes, the EPR spectrum of the electrogenerated reduced complex

was studied at 120 K. The monoanionic complex $[1]^-$, generated by exhaustive electrolysis at -0.50 V, showed an axial (nearly isotropic; inset, Fig. 4) signal at $g = 2.001/1.977$, confirming the formation of a radical upon reduction. The anion radical complexes of transition metals are known to often have a slight axial character and g values slightly deviating from 2.0023 due to metal-ligand interactions³¹. Accordingly, it is reasonable that unpaired spin resides primarily on the ligands (see DFT calculation). Unfortunately, however, no ^{14}N hyperfine coupling was observed in the EPR spectrum, at 120 K. However, the metal-centered oxidation at $+1.42$ V ($\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$) of the above complex was irreversible and is attributed to degradation of the complex upon electron transfer.

DFT and TD-DFT :

Density functional theory was employed to look into the electronic structure of the complexes **1** and $[1]^-$. The optimized metrical parameters of **1** matched well with that of experimentally observed values and the optimized bond distances and coordinates are given in Tables 2 and Supplementary Table S1 respectively. The analysis of molecular orbitals showed that HOMO is mainly localized over the Ru-center (38%) and carbonate anion (42%) while the LUMO is localized over the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ azo (52%) function and pyridyl moiety (38%).

The one electron reduced complex, $[1]^-$ is optimized and the optimized metrical parameters are tabulated in Table 2 and the coordinates are submitted as Supplementary material (Table S2). The notable feature is the elongation of $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ distances compared to the isolated neutral complex. The $d_{\text{N-N}}$ (average) in the reduced complex is 1.337 Å due to delocalization^{5c,9c} of 1-charge over the two ligands. The spin density plot clearly indicates that unpaired spin (α) resides on the two azo functions and small fraction on the pyridyl moiety. Some opposite spin (β) is localized on the Ru-atom which causes small anisotropy in the EPR spectrum of $[1]^-$.

The complex **1** is moderately soluble in common organic solvent and exhibits several absorptions in the UV-Vis region with a strong band at 620 nm along with a broad transition near 860 nm (Table 3, Fig. 7). To gather information on the origin of these transitions, we have analyzed the B3LYP/SDD/6-311G(d)/6-31G(d)-optimized geometries of complex (**1**). On the basis of values of the oscillator strength predicted by using time-dependent DFT

Fig. 5. Frontier molecular orbital of the complex **1**.

Fig. 6. Spin density plot for $[1]^-$.

(TD-DFT), the broad transition at 860 nm for compound **1** is ascribed to excitation, HOMO \rightarrow LUMO which appeared (calculated) at 818 nm. The HOMO is localized over the Ru-center (38%) and carbonate function (42%) where as LUMO is mainly localized over the azo functions (90%). The most intense transition at 620 nm is due

Fig. 7. UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra of the compound **1** in 10^{-4} M dichloromethane solution.

to HOMO-1→LUMO transition : for comparison, the TD-DFT value appeared at 580 nm. The HOMO-1 is mainly localized on the Ru-center (39%) and carbonate function (28%).

Conclusion

The present work has demonstrated a yet another redox induced chemical transformation involving activation of coordinated CO by oxygen. Herein, a nucleophilic attack by *in situ* generated O_2^{2-} on coordinated carbon monoxide produces a ruthenium carbonate complex. The synthetic protocol is eccentric and different from the conventional preparative procedure of the carbonate complexes. The ruthenium carbonate complex has been neatly characterized using several physical studies and single crystal X-ray structure determination.

Supporting information

CCDC 910622 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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